

Improvement of Interfacial Shear Strength Using Electrostatically Deposited Silica Nano-particles

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1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRPs) are a class of materials that can have very high strength, stiffness and low density, making them appealing materials for aerospace, automotive and sporting goods industries. FRPs are often comprised of high strength, high modulus fibers, embedded in a polymeric matrix, however, the mechanical properties of the FRP are not determined only by the fiber and matrix, but also the adhesion and interphase between them. It is well understood that the adhesion must be optimized to achieve the best mechanical properties possible for a given fiber/matrix system [1],[2]. In the case of glass fibers, and often carbon fibers, the adhesion is controlled and improved using silane coupling agents such as glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPS) and aminoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (APS), for example. The use of chemical interphase modifiers has been the subject of extensive research for decades [3].

Alternatively, the interphase can be modified by introducing nano, or possibly micro, whiskers or particles to the fiber surface. It is possible to grow interphase structural modifiers directly on to the fiber surface. As early as 1974, there has been work on modifying carbon fiber with Si_3N_4 , TiO_2 and SiC whiskers [4]. Tensile and interlaminar shear strengths were improved but in plane properties were reduced, due to fiber damage caused by high temperature processing. There has been significant interest in growing carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on carbon fibers using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) techniques [5], [6]. However, the harsh environment of CVD damages carbon fibers, reducing their strength, thus limiting the feasibility of commercialization. ZnO whiskers have been grown on carbon fibers, but under benign

reaction conditions that do not degrade the fiber strength [7], [8], [9]. These ZnO whiskers improved the interfacial shear strength (IFSS), interlaminar shear strength and modulus of the systems tested. Additional surface roughness on glass fibers has been achieved by treatment with a tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS)/GPS blend, with the intention of improving mechanical interlock at the interface [10]. The energy absorption during a microdroplet shear test and the IFSS were increased. Instead of growing structures on the surface of fibers, it is possible to synthesize interphase modifiers separately and to deposit them on the surface. CNTs were deposited on to carbon fiber surfaces using electrophoresis, leading to an increase in interlaminar shear strength [11]. CNTs treated with poly(ethyleneimine) (PEI) were electrostatically deposited on to carbon fibers, modestly increasing the IFSS [12]. 22 nm silica particles were incorporated into a sizing package, with other adhesion modifiers, to improve the impact energy absorption of an E-glass composite [13], [14].

Previously, our laboratory has investigated the effects on IFSS, strength and modulus, in E-glass/poly(vinyl butyral) systems when modifying the interphase with polymeric core-shell particles, where the shell and core consisted of poly(ethyleneimine) (PEI) and poly(styrene), respectively [2]. Two different diameters were investigated, 143 nm and 327 nm. The 327 nm particles led to only a modest improvement in properties, while 143 nm particles increased the IFSS and longitudinal tensile modulus and strength by 56%, 42% and 34%, respectively. This enhancement was attributed to increasing the modulus and toughness of the interphase. A high matrix shear modulus has been shown to increase the IFSS [15] and, based on a finite element analysis

study, an interphase with a higher modulus can lead to higher fiber axial stress [16]. At fiber ends, there is an apparent infinite shear stress at the fiber/matrix interface, when the matrix has a lower modulus than the fiber under axial load. Thus, in order to mitigate debonding, the interphase must not only have high strength, but must also be tough.

The present study sought to investigate how PEI functionalized silica nano-particles, electrostatically deposited to E-glass fibers, affected the IFSS of a single fiber composite, as a function of particle size. Mineral oxide nano-particles have been shown to increase the Young's modulus and toughness in certain thermosets [17], [18]. Although work has been done previously on particle covered fiber composites, there has been no systematic investigation into the effects of particle size, nor has the use of silica/PEI core-shell type interphase modifiers been studied. The particle size determines the toughness and modulus of the interphase, the degree of bonding between the particle and fiber, and the thickness of interphase that is modified. The significance of particle/fiber covalent bonding was explored by varying the fiber surface functionality. The importance of pH, electrolyte concentration and particle volume fraction on producing optimum surface coverage was also explored.

2 Methods

2.1 Materials

E-glass fibers were supplied as sized tows by Fiberex Inc. (Leduc, Alberta, Canada). Individual fibers had a diameter of $11 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$. Desizing was performed with NoChromix (Godax Laboratories, Cabin John, MD) and concentrated sulphuric acid. Fibers were functionalized with 3-glycidyloxypropyltriethoxysilane (GPS) (Gelest Inc, Morrisville, PA) in 190 proof ethanol with glacial acetic acid to reduce the pH to 4.5.

Four different silica nano-particles were used, 16 nm Ludox SM-30, 26 nm Ludox TMA (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO), 71 nm Nexsil 85A (Nyacol, Ashland, MO), and 100 nm (Fiber Optic Center, New Bedford, MA). The referenced particle sizes for the three smallest silica particles were determined by dynamic light scattering (90Plus, Brookhaven Instruments Corp, Holtzville, NY), the diameter of the 100 nm particles was provided by

the manufacturer. The particles were functionalized with trimethoxysilane modified poly(ethyleneimine) (SPEI) (Gelest Inc), molecular weight 1,500 – 1,800 g/mol. Deionized water (DI H₂O) was used as a solvent, glacial acetic acid was used to reduce the pH to 4.5.

The particles were electrostatically deposited on the fibers in DI H₂O, with dilute potassium hydroxide and nitric acid to adjust the pH, and potassium nitrate was used to alter the ionic strength.

Fibers were embedded in a matrix of a stoichiometric ratio of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (Epon 828, Miller-Stephenson, Danbury, CT) and m-phenylenediamine (mPDA, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO).

2.2 Fiber Functionalization

E-glass fibers were desized as tows by soaking in NoChromix and concentrated sulfuric acid for 90 minutes. The fibers were rinsed with DI H₂O, then dried at 100°C for several hours. Individual fibers were removed from the tow and mounted on a handling jig. 0.5 vol% GPS was hydrolyzed in 190 proof ethanol for 20 minutes with sufficient acetic acid to reduce the pH to 4.5. The fibers were submerged for 60 minutes then dried at room temperature. For comparison, one set of fibers was functionalized with SPEI. The functionalization procedure was identical, except 0.5 vol% SPEI was used instead of GPS.

2.3 Nano-particle Functionalization

1 wt% silica nano-particles were dispersed in DI H₂O with vigorous stirring followed by 5 minutes of ultrasonication with a Sonifier 250 with a cup horn attachment (Branson Ultrasonics Corp., Danbury, CT). The amount of SPEI used to functionalize each batch was 0.5 vol% or calculated from the approximate number of moles of hydroxyl functional groups on the surface, whichever was larger. The manufacturer reported values for surface area for SM-30, TMA, Nexsil 85A, and 100 nm silica were 400, 140, 55, and 6 m²/g, respectively. Assuming a hydroxyl surface coverage of 5 OH nm⁻² [3], the approximate molar concentration of surface hydroxyl groups can be determined. Assuming that one SPEI molecule reacts with one hydroxyl surface

group, the amount of SPEI needed for each particle type was 5.80, 2.03, 0.8 and 0.5 vol%, for 16, 26, 71 and 100 nm particles, respectively. The SPEI was added dropwise with vigorous mixing, and the pH was reduced to 4.5 with acetic acid. Flocculation occurred with the addition of SPEI which was dispersed by sonicating for 15 minutes (Model 8848, Cole-Parmer, Vernon Hills, IL). The suspension was mixed for an additional 45 min.

After functionalization, the suspensions were purified. The 16 and 26 nm particles were dialyzed with regenerated cellulose dialysis tubing (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA), with a nominal pore size of 4.8 nm which retains materials with a M.W. of 12,000 g/mol or higher. The suspension was dialyzed in DI H₂O until the conductivity remained constant with time, typically four days. The suspensions were diluted to 0.1 vol% in DI H₂O.

The larger particles, 71 and 100 nm, were centrifuged at 7,500 RPM for 15 minutes and 5,500 for 10 minutes, respectively. The supernatant was removed, an equivalent amount of DI H₂O was added, the particles were redispersed and centrifuged again to “rinse” the particles. Finally, the particles were redispersed in DI H₂O and diluted to achieve 0.1 vol% solids.

2.4 Particle Deposition on Fibers

The SPEI functionalized particles had a positive charge, and the fibers, even when GPS functionalized, had a negative charge, in water in the pH range of interest. The pH was adjusted to 7.0 using KOH and HNO₃. The opposing electrical potential caused the particles to spontaneously deposit on the surface of the fiber. However, to achieve optimum surface coverage, it was necessary to add salt. KNO₃ was added to the suspensions at concentrations of 0.75, 0.75, 0.015, and 0.05 M for 16, 26, 71 and 100 nm silica, respectively. The 0.1 vol% SPEI functionalized silica suspensions were heated to 85°C, and the GPS functionalized fibers were submerged for 60 s. The fibers were then rinsed with DI H₂O to remove any residual salt. The optimum conditions for surface coverage (KNO₃ concentration, pH, particle volume fraction, and submersion duration) were determined by systematically varying each variable independently, then making qualitative observations from scanning

electron microscope (SEM) (JSM 7000, JEOL, Akishima, Japan) images.

2.5 Single Fiber Composite Specimen Preparation

Individual fibers were suspended across a dog-bone style silicone mold, shown in Fig. 1. A stoichiometric amount of EP-828 and mPDA were mixed for 10 minutes at 800 RPM at 75°C. 0.8 ml was pipetted into the mold cavities and cured at 75°C for 2 hours and post cured at 125°C for an additional 2 hours.

2.6 Single Fiber Fragmentation Test

A dog-bone sample was placed a miniature tensile test frame (St. John’s Computer Machine, St. John’s, MI), which was mounted to a microscope, shown in Fig. 2. Tensile strain was applied at 0.003 mm/mm minute. Generally, fiber fragmentation started at a strain of 8% and reached the critical length, l_c , at 10%. The fiber critical length is the minimum fiber length for which sufficient shear stress transfer can occur to cause fiber failure and is equal to 4/3 the average fiber length, l_m . The samples were strained to 12%. At least 5 samples were tested for each system; 10 samples was typical. After straining, a 25mm slide cover was placed on the sample to act as a consistent measure of the gauge length, and the fiber breaks were counted.

The IFSS was determined using the Kelly-Tyson model [19], where the IFSS is the maximum shear stress, τ , and is given by:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_{f,c} d}{2l_c}$$

where $\sigma_{f,c}$ is the tensile strength of the fiber, and d is the fiber diameter.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Surface Coverage as a Function of pH

By controlling the electrostatics of the particles and fibers, it is possible to control the extent of particle coverage on the fibers. The amine groups of the SPEI cause the functionalized particles to take on a positive surface charge, and the

hydroxyl groups on the E-glass fibers cause the fibers to have a negative surface charge, in water, over a large pH range. Thus, when the fibers are submerged in a suspension of SPEI functionalized particles, they will spontaneously deposit to the fiber surface. To determine the optimum pH, GPS functionalized fibers were dipped in 0.1 vol% 100 nm SPEI functionalized silica suspensions with pH varied from 4.4 to 9.2; afterwards the surfaces were imaged with SEM. Representative micrographs are shown in Fig. 3. A pH of 7 gave the best surface coverage.

3.2 Surface Coverage as a Function of Salt Concentration

Adjusting the pH was not sufficient for obtaining a monolayer of particles, assumed to be the optimal case. Fig. 3b shows the large interparticle spacing on the fiber surface. This large spacing is caused by the electrostatic repulsion between particles, preventing the deposition of close neighbors. The range of electrical potential is related to the Debye length, κ^{-1} , or the “screening length;” it is the distance from the particle surface over which the electrical potential has fallen to 1/e (0.378) of its surface potential. It can be calculated by:

$$\kappa^{-1} = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon\epsilon_0 kT}{2e^2 z^2 n_\infty}}$$

where ϵ is dielectric constant of the medium, ϵ_0 is permittivity of free space, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, e is the protonic charge, z is the valence of the background electrolyte and n_∞ is the number density of the electrolyte. Thus, by adding an electrolyte, such as KNO_3 , the range of electrostatic repulsion can be reduced, then, by Brownian motion, the particles can approach and occupy areas near particles already on the surface, increasing the surface coverage of particles on the fiber surface. KNO_3 was chosen as an electrolyte because neither ion specifically adsorbs to the fiber or particle surfaces.

The optimum salt concentration was determined for each particle size by systematically varying the concentration, coating GPS functionalized fibers, and making observations using SEM. An example of the surface coverage dependence on electrolyte concentration is shown in

Fig. 4, where the KNO_3 concentration is varied from 0 – 0.75 M. The optimum KNO_3 concentrations for 16, 26, 71 and 100 nm particles were 0.75, 0.75, 0.015 and 0.05 M, respectively. Example micrographs of the particle coating on fibers, for each particle size, using the optimum KNO_3 concentration, are shown in Fig. 5. For the two smallest particle sizes, the volume of electrical double layer was sufficient to cause depletion of bulk concentration, necessitating large amounts of KNO_3 .

3.3 Interfacial Shear Strength

The strength of the bond between the polymer matrix and glass fibers was determined by single fiber fragmentation tests. It is understood that removing the fiber sizing decrease the strength, and treating with silanes increases the strength, however the manufacturer’s reported value for strength was used in the calculations. The fiber diameters were determined via SEM. The IFSS for as received, bare (desized), GPS functionalized, SPEI functionalized and GPS functionalized with 16, 26, 71 and 100 nm SPEI functionalized particles are shown in Fig. 6. These results, and others discussed in the next section, are also tabulated in Table 1.

There was no apparent change in IFSS when the sizing was removed, because the fiber ultimate strength was reduced from micro-damage inflicted during handling, (which would typically be prevented by the sizing) while increasing the adhesion. Although sizings contain adhesion promoters, they also contain processing aids that reduce the IFSS relative to a bare fiber.

Treating bare fibers with GPS increased the IFSS by 20% as it forms a crosslinked interphase covalently bound to the matrix, affording good adhesion. The SPEI functionalization increased the IFSS as much as GPS, as it also covalently bonds to both the fiber and matrix. This is fortuitous because changes in IFSS in systems with SPEI functionalized particles can be attributed to the addition of particles to the interphase, not simply a change in surface chemistry.

The 26 nm SPEI functionalized silica particles on GPS functionalized fibers increased the IFSS 32% over bare fibers, and 10% over GPS fibers, with no particles. This improvement was attributed to an increase in the toughness and

modulus of the interphase while still permitting good bonding between the matrix and fiber.

The 71 and 100 nm particles decreased the IFSS 5% and 26%, respectively, when compared to GPS functionalized fibers. These larger particle sizes likely decrease the toughness of the interphase and act as surface flaws, decreasing the adhesive strength.

The 16 nm particles decreased the IFSS 6% compared to GPS functionalized fibers. If the particles were too small to significantly affect the interphase it would be expected that the IFSS would be an intermediate value between the GPS and SPEI functionalized fibers. However, surface treating fibers with the particle suspensions invariably introduces imperfections, mostly in the form of aggregates, that reduce the IFSS. An example of these aggregates, indicated with arrows, for 16 nm particle coated fibers is shown in Fig. 7.

SPEI functionalized 26 nm particles were also deposited on sized and bare fibers. The IFSS of these systems, and the same fiber functionalizations without particles, are shown in Fig. 8, and given in Table 1. It was postulated that the poly(ethyleneimine) on the particles could covalently bond to the epoxy rings on the GPS functionalized fibers. If this bonding was significant, the increase in IFSS for SPEI particles on GPS functionalized fibers would be greater than SPEI particles on bare and sized fibers.

Depositing the functionalized 26 nm particles on sized and bare fibers increased the IFSS 13%, in both cases. With GPS functionalized fibers the IFSS was increased 10%. Therefore, covalent bonding between the fiber and particles did not significantly contribute to the IFSS. The improvement in IFSS with the addition of 26 nm particles was solely the result of increasing the interphase modulus and toughness.

3.4 Micromechanical Failure

Transmitted, visible light microscopy images were taken of the fiber ends, after a single fiber fragmentation test. The images permit qualitative assessment of the adhesive strength between the fiber and matrix. An example, showing the fiber ends of GPS fibers and GPS fibers with 26 nm SPEI particles is shown in Fig. 9.

A debonded region near the fiber end can be seen in Fig 9a. The addition of 26 nm SPEI functionalized particles to the interphase increased the adhesion between the fiber and matrix, preventing debonding. Optical micrographs were taken of all systems studied. Systems with a low IFSS showed large debonded regions, while systems with high IFSS showed less or no debonding.

4 Conclusions

Trimethoxysilane modified poly(ethyleneimine) functionalized silica nanoparticles can be an effective means to improve the interfacial shear stress transfer between E-glass fibers and a matrix of m-phenylenediamine and the BADGE epoxy EP-828. Using functionalized 26 nm particles on a GPS functionalized fiber the IFSS was increased 32% over bare fibers, and 10% over GPS functionalized fibers. The IFSS is highly sensitive to particle size, small particles (16 nm) have little effect on IFSS while larger particles (71 and 100 nm) can reduce the IFSS significantly. The improvement in IFSS was likely caused by an improvement in interphase modulus and toughness.

Obtaining uniform, dense coverage of the SPEI functionalized particles on the fiber surfaces was achieved by carefully controlling the electrostatics. The pH was adjusted to 7, to achieve a strong negative surface charge on the fibers and a strong positive surface charge on the functionalized particles. Varying amounts of KNO_3 were added to reduce the range of electrostatic repulsion between the particles, increasing the surface coverage on the fibers, leading to monolayer coverage.

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Figures

Fig 1. A schematic of a dog-bone sample; the dimensions are in mm

Fig 2. The miniature tensile test frame, mounted to a transmitted light microscope

Fig 3. SPEI functionalized 100 nm silica particles on a GPS functionalized fiber with a pH of a) 9.2, b) 7.0, and c) 4.4

Fig 4. The change in surface coverage of SPEI functionalized 26 nm silica particles on GPS functionalized fibers with a KNO_3 concentration of a) 0, b) 0.01, c) 0.05, d) 0.25 and e) 0.75 M.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of GPS glass fibers with a) 100 nm, b) 71 nm, c) 26 and d) 16 nm SPEI particles deposited on the surface, using optimum KNO_3 concentrations

Fig 6. The IFSS for sized (as received), bare (desized), GPS functionalized, SPEI functionalized and GPS functionalized with 16, 26, 71 and 100 nm SPEI functionalized particles

Fig 8. IFSS values of sized, bare and GPS functionalized E-glass fibers with and without SPEI functionalized 26 nm silica particles

Fig 7. Aggregates on the surface of a fiber, deposited during coating of 16 nm SPEI functionalized particles

Table 1. The IFSS values and standard deviations for E-glass fibers, with different surface treatments, embedded in a matrix of mPDA and EP-828

	IFSS [MPa]	Standard deviation [MPa]
Sized	9.0	0.9
Bare	9.0	0.1
GPS	10.8	1.4
SPEI	11.1	0.7
16 nm/GPS	10.1	0.6
26 nm/GPS	11.9	0.4
71 nm/GPS	10.3	0.4
100 nm/GPS	8.0	0.6
26 nm/bare	10.1	1.6
26 nm/sized	10.2	0.6

Fig 9. Optical micrographs of a GPS fiber a) without particle modified interphase and b) with a 26 nm SPEI functionalized particle modified interphase